

Re-Engineering Wimsatt for Limited Beings

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Abstract

Science is the best way to produce facts about reality. The best, at least, that limited human beings have devised so far. Yet, not even scientists quite seem to understand how scientific knowledge is generated. This is not only a philosophical but also a practical problem, as our misunderstandings affect the quality of our research and limit the directions it can take. In light of this, it may be good if we reflected a bit more on how we do science — to become better researchers through philosophy. Here, I provide an accessible introduction to a philosophical approach that achieves precisely this: William Wimsatt's *multi-perspectival realism*. It disabuses us of widespread but misleading myths and idealizations about science, such as the idea that everything in the world can be reduced to a fundamental level, or that we can approach a “view from nowhere” — complete and objectively detached knowledge of the world. Wimsatt proposes an alternative view based on his thorough studies of actual research practice. It cuts deeply into the layered yet messy structure of reality, and the improvised but potent tools we have available, as limited and evolved beings, to explore it. Wimsatt reframes science as an irregular yet adaptive process rather than a cumulative repository of unalterable facts. His philosophy provides a workable and grounded middle way between radical skepticism and naïve belief in the objective truth of science. It explains how knowledge *is* conceptually constructed by humans, but still connects us to reality in a trustworthy way. We need such a new view of science, not only to improve our research practices and outcomes but, more generally, to gain a more realistic understanding of ourselves, the world, and our place and role within it.

Keywords: philosophy of science, theory of knowledge, epistemology, ontology, research practice, scientific perspectivism, multi-perspectival realism, heuristics, bounded rationality, nothing-but-ism, reductionism, special sciences, piecewise engineering, rainforest ontology, levels of organization, non-aggregativity, emergence, robustness, generative entrenchment, metabolism of errors, perspective, complexity, causal thicket

Introduction: why should scientists care about philosophy?

"Why is it that academics who claim to seek the truth want to pretend that they have always had it? What are they paid for, anyway?" (Wimsatt, 2007, p.3)

William Wimsatt is not only one of the most important philosophers of science of the late 20th and early 21st centuries, but he may also be one of the most underrated. Why, I wonder, is he rarely cited by philosophers, especially those outside the philosophy of biology? I will leave it to the other contributors of this volume to assess this strange situation.

Instead, my target audience are practicing researchers in the special sciences — empiricists and theoreticians alike: no matter whether you are a biologist, neuroscientist, psychologist, AI researcher, complexity scientist, geologist, anthropologist, sociologist, or economist, or even a chemist or condensed-matter physicist, what Wimsatt has to say seems important, even crucial, for you to know. It should be a core part of your scientific training. I'm dead serious about this: not only does he provide profound insights into how knowledge *is* generated and justified, but he also reveals some serious misconceptions and blind spots when it comes to how research *ought to be done* in all these fields. Once you have read and digested his work, you will not only better understand what you are doing, but you will do it differently, producing more trustworthy and useful knowledge in the process. This is why you, as a working scientist, should read on: *to become a better researcher through philosophy*.

This is what good philosophy of science is all about: it not only *describes* what scientists do, but it also *prescribes*. "An adequate philosophy of science should have normative force" (Wimsatt, 2007, p.26). It aims not only to understand but also to help improve how we *do* science. Its task, in particular, is to help us find and avoid errors in our methods and thinking. In turn, philosophy allows itself to be improved, constantly, through the latest scientific insights and innovations. And it pays close attention to how science is actually done.

This kind of philosophy is not exactly mainstream, but we need more of it, because it is useful and relevant. Philosophers call it *naturalism*. It adjusts its views to reality, instead of vice versa. It sees science and philosophy as going hand in hand. They co-evolve, in close touch with each other. They never stop learning from one another. And they are essential allies in our quest to get a better grip on reality, a grip that can all too easily slip and, in any case, always could be made tighter than it currently is. Scientific progress will never stop. We won't ever wake up, one sunny day, and realize that we know everything about the world that there is for us to know. This is one of Wimsatt's most basic and, to me, most empowering insights: we will never run out of work, because there will always be more fascinating discoveries to be made.

In addition, he will also cure you of *physics envy*: the idea that all sciences should look up to, and ultimately mature into, something like fundamental physics with its rigorously formalized methodologies and “universal laws.” Such envy can bear strange fruit, like the untimely and inappropriate mathematization of neoclassical economics with its rational-choice models of human behavior. This unfounded application of oversimplified formalisms — a mere imitation of “hard science” — gives a veneer of respectability to work based on such models without, however, connecting to the messy reality underneath in any reliable or meaningful way.

There is a basic misunderstanding here: fundamental physics, however successful it may be in its own domain, is *not* a good model for any other branch of science. Instead, we could consider it (if we were so inclined) as the peculiar kind of science that chose all the easy problems first. It began by studying and modeling some of the most general, regular, obvious, and robustly detectable phenomena in the universe. In contrast, the subject matter of the special sciences is of a more unruly kind: what happens tends to be particular, variable, subtle, and highly dependent on context. Clearly, then, each field requires its own approach, and each approach its own philosophy. There is no unity to the sciences.

The mistake some physicists and philosophers make is to believe that we could one day find a limited and unique set of universal laws that cover *everything* in the world. Or, at least, that all the lesser phenomena of the special sciences could be derived from such laws in the end. Wimsatt, borrowing from physicist Richard Feynman (1965), calls this axiomatic path the *Greek or Euclidean approach* to scientific theory, but finds it lacking as a realistic vision. Instead, he favors Feynman’s pragmatic *Babylonian path*: what anchors our knowledge in reality is not abstract general laws, but concrete and specific insights that can be accessed or produced in many independent ways. What is fundamental and real is not a matter of abstraction, but a matter of *good practice*. There isn’t a singular keystone holding up the entire edifice of our knowledge, but much broader networked support with relatively short chains of inference.

Granted, this may not be as simple or elegant as the lofty Greek vision. But at least it’s achievable, adaptive and, at the same time, less prone to collapse. It is a vision for a science suitable for limited beings living in a large and messy world. And it is exactly what the special sciences are designed for: Wimsatt’s philosophy is a *theory of practice*, and that is why it is so relevant and useful to working scientists.

Yet, it needs to be said: one significant obstacle hindering the wider dissemination of Wimsatt’s work is that it is not exactly accessible, especially if you are not a trained philosopher. The main source for his wisdom, the 2007 book “*Re-Engineering Philosophy for Limited Beings*,” consists of 450 pages of dense philosophical argumentation, endless lists of enumerated points (that

sometimes run out of the letters of the alphabet), dozens of meticulously described case studies from different areas of biology, and footnotes so rich in content that each could serve as the seed for a doctoral thesis. And although the book features a reader-friendly introductory Part I, Parts II and III are mainly a collection of previously published essays on a wide range of different topics. This certainly doesn't help improve the overall flow of the reading experience.

For this reason, I — as a practicing biologist — want to *re-engineer Wimsatt for limited beings* in the space of this article: I want to make the main points of his work easily accessible to you — working scientists without any background or prior interest in philosophy. All it takes is a few hours of your time, not weeks or even months of sweat, tears, and toil. I strive for an easy reading experience without losing too much of Wimsatt's depth. And I promise: when you have digested his ideas, your life and work will never be the same again. You will see the world with different eyes. Bill's work has deeply transformed me: not only has he made me a better researcher, but I now feel more at home in this world, at ease with its (and my own) messiness.

So let's begin our journey. We'll first establish the basic principles of a science for limited beings in a large world, then dive into a number of Wimsattian key concepts — levels of organization and non-aggregativity, heuristics, robustness, perspectives and piecewise approximations, the metabolism of errors, generative entrenchment, causal thickets, nothing-but-ism, and the ontology of the tropical rainforest. In the end, we will see that *human knowledge is engineered*, with all the fallibility and bias this brings with it, but that not all is lost: even as limited beings, we *can* get a grip on reality, and we can make that grip increasingly robust and useful. We *can* generate scientific knowledge that may not be perfect, but is definitely good enough for us.

1. Premise: limited beings in a large world

"We aren't God and we don't have a God's-eye view of the world." (Wimsatt, 2007, p.6)

It is extremely unlikely that humans, or any other intelligent beings that evolved as a part of this universe, will ever have complete and certain knowledge of pretty much anything, no matter how good their science will ever become. The idea of *absolute knowledge* is an *idealization*. And not a very helpful one. Still, it is an idea that is tough to kill: even if we are intuitively aware of our limitations, illusions of detached objectivity and omniscience remain tempting and persuasive.

This does not mean, however, that any way of knowing is as good as any other, as some critics of science claim. "The sciences are the best-crafted repositories of truth on this planet" (Wimsatt, 2007, p.4). I agree. Science is our most trustworthy connection with a reality that is larger than us — far beyond our grasp or control. Moreover, it is our most powerful tool to

tease apart the causal structure of this reality. We definitely need *more* science, not less. But what we also need is an explicit and accurate account of how limited beings like us generate reliable knowledge of the world. Or, in Wimsatt's words: "[w]e need a philosophy of science that can be pursued by *real* people in *real* situations in *real* time with the kinds of tools that they *actually* have — now or in a realistically possible future." (*ibid.*, p.5, *original emphasis*). This is as good as it will ever get. Perfect knowledge is not on the menu for imperfect creatures.

The problem is: for most of its history, philosophy has tried very hard *not* to accept but to *transcend* our limited nature as human beings when coming up with *epistemologies*— theories that explain how we generate reliable knowledge. In fact, a favorite pastime of philosophers has been to advance seemingly foolproof and general accounts of what knowledge is in the abstract. Take, for example, Plato's classical definition of knowledge as "justified true belief" (from his *Theaetetus*). It is as intuitively appealing as it is useless in practice. What does it mean for a belief to be "justified?" And how can we be certain it is "true?" We can quibble about such matters until the cows come home. But even worse: Plato was also defeated on logical grounds by Edmund Gettier (1963) who formulated two short and simple counterexamples, now called *Gettier cases*, which are instances of "justified true belief" that are clearly *not* knowledge.

A similar fate has befallen *every* such foundational theory of knowledge, including those of logical positivism (reviewed in Creath, 2023) and Karl Popper (see Thornton, 2023), which are outdated today but still the most popular epistemologies among practicing scientists. These principled but abstract accounts were criticized by philosophers and historians like Thomas Kuhn (1962; see also Bird, 2025), Imre Lakatos (1970; see Musgrave & Pigden, 2023), or Stephen Brush (1974) who were highlighting the messiness and contingency of actual scientific discovery. This culminated in the epistemic anarchism of Paul Feyerabend (1975; see Oberheim & Preston, 2025) who declared himself "against method," with scientific "progress" just one accident after another. No matter how far we are willing to buy into this line of criticism, it is clear that abstract epistemologies are less applicable and more limited than its proponents would want us to know. Plus, like Plato's account, they also contain logical inconsistencies. And yet, many philosophers and scientists cling on to absolutist ideas, often fearful of losing the authority that the illusion of immutable and objective scientific facts conveys, especially in public debates on science.

It was against the background of these intellectual tensions that Wimsatt started formulating his arguments in the late 1960s and early 1970s. He was neither satisfied with claims that science could achieve absolute and universal truths (or that it approaches such truths in an asymptotic manner — what philosophers call *metaphysical* or *objectivist realism*), nor that scientific progress was arbitrary or entirely driven by social and historical circumstances

(*constructivist relativism*). Luckily, there is a middle way: Wimsatt's *theory of practice*. It retains the widespread and useful belief (especially among scientists) that research actually *can* and *does* connect to a reality beyond our current grasp but, at the same time, also acknowledges that knowledge *is* culturally and historically constructed. Like any other tool or artifact that humans have invented, scientific knowledge is *engineered*, but it is built in a way that is both adaptively robust and applicable across a wide range of situations. Wimsatt calls this philosophy of his *multi-perspectival realism*.

There are other philosophers of science who started thinking in similar, perspectivist terms. Examples include Roy Bhaskar (1975) and his *critical realism*, which mainly caught on in the philosophy of the social sciences, Ian Hacking (1983), Nancy Cartwright (1983, 1999), John Dupré (1993), and other members of the "*Stanford School*" (reviewed in Ludwig & Ruphy, 2024), who argued for the disunity of the sciences, or Ronald Giere (1999, 2006), who provocatively proposed a model-based "*science without laws*" and a theory of *scientific perspectivism*. For many years, these views did not garner enough mainstream attention. This may finally be changing, even inside the philosophy of physics (*e.g.*, Massimi & McCoy, 2020; Massimi, 2022), which is good news. It is high time that the perspectivist argument is taken more seriously among philosophers. And it is even more important that scientists start learning about it.

This argument — despite differences between accounts — points to a solid central insight: *scientific realism* is not absolute or metaphysical, but only *local* and *piecemeal*. Scientific knowledge connects to reality at times, more or less, here and there. Such softening of the hardness of science triggers a red flag for many researchers. So, let's examine what it means exactly, and why it is the best a limited intelligence can hope for in a large, bewildering world.

As a first step, we ask: who is the knower? After all, we are interested in a theory of knowledge suitable for *limited beings* like us. There must be *somebody* who is both the source and the target of knowledge. The "target" part is straightforward: knowledge should not only be robust and accurate but also *useful* and *understandable*. It must be adjusted to the knower's needs, to their physical, sensory, and cognitive capacities, and must help them take appropriate action in situations they tend to find themselves in. The "source" part is equally simple, yet we forget about it all too often: our personal and collective knowledge arises *exclusively* from *experience* — ours and that of other humans and, at a basic innate level, that of our ancestors as well. It is shaped by our biological and cultural evolution. This kind of knowledge requires *subjects* which are the physical loci of experience in the world. We call such subjects "*selves*." It makes no sense to talk about knowledge without considering these selves as knowers.

Wimsatt says little about the kind of physical system that can be a self, so I'll provide some context. This helps us ground his thinking further in the insights of contemporary science. To begin with, we must agree that knowers are themselves a part of the natural world and, thus, are both subjects *and* objects of knowledge. Ignoring this strange loop (Hofstadter, 2007) easily leads to misunderstandings and blind spots, and may tempt us to consider our abstract theories about the world (our "*maps*") more real than our experiences (our only access to the "*territory*" to be mapped; Frank et al., 2024).

The situation *is* somewhat paradoxical: for knowledge to be possible, we must be subjects that are set apart from the rest of the world — the objects to be known. At the same time, we are continuous with our environment in many ways. Our boundaries are porous and this is essential to who we are: not only do we rely on material, energetic, and sensory inputs for our survival, but we literally *become* those inputs in the process. You are what you eat, and your experiences constructively constitute who you are as a person. To make matters worse, it is difficult to define precisely where our lives begin and where they end. In addition, we also alter our environment through our actions. Thus, there is an *epistemic cut* in our reality, a necessary and sharp distinction between subject and object, but *ontologically* (in terms of our very being) we are deeply intertwined and radically open to our surroundings, our boundaries notoriously ill-defined (see also Rosen, 1991; Pattee & Rączaszek-Leonardi, 2012).

Moreover, unlike inert objects or mechanisms, living beings are precarious — always on the brink of existence. They are the kind of natural system that must continually and actively invest *physical work* to maintain its own organization (Kauffman, 2000). All far-from-equilibrium systems extract work from local free-energy gradients. But instead of just dissipating this energy (as in an eddie, or a candle flame), living systems channel it back to constrain the collective co-construction of the physical processes that constitute themselves (*e.g.*, Deacon, 2011; Montévil & Mossio, 2015; Roli et al., 2022; Jaeger, 2024a; Jaeger et al., 2024). This results in a hierarchical cyclical process called *autopoiesis* (Varela, 1979; Maturana & Varela, 1987) and the characteristic *self-manufacturing organization* of a living being (Hofmeyr, 2021). When autopoiesis ceases, the body may still take some time to decay, but the system is no longer alive, and no longer the subject of experience.

Why is this relevant here? First, in a large world with an open future (see below), an autopoietic system can construct itself to develop in various directions, depending on — but not determined by — its current and past environment. It acquires a certain *autonomy* from its surroundings through constructive *self-constraint* (Moreno & Mossio, 2015; Montévil & Mossio, 2015). Second, which way it develops may depend on an internal "model" — not necessarily a representation but, more broadly, some kind of internalized expectation about the

environment. This renders the system *anticipatory* and no longer merely *reactive* like a mechanism (Rosen, 1985). Autonomy and anticipation imply that a living being (and only a living being) has a certain degree of control over its own fate: it becomes a *goal-oriented agent* (Roli et al., 2022; Jaeger, 2024a; Jaeger et al., 2024). It can act on its own behalf in ways that are conducive to its continued existence. But without accurate and adequate internal models that are properly aligned with its environment, it cannot survive or (eventually) evolve. Such models can be biologically hardwired and adjusted by brute force, through trial and error plus adaptation by natural selection. Or, in the case of intelligent knowers like us humans, we can improve them through learning. We can let our models die in our own stead. This is how they create *understanding*. And science is the most effective way to do this: the skillful craft of collectively generating and testing particularly sophisticated, reliable, and actionable models of our world.

However, a word of caution is in order at this point: I've warned above against mistaking map and territory. We do this, for instance, when we claim that the laws of physics *are* reality, rather than an admittedly very robust and general way to *describe* and *predict* real phenomena. The same mistake happens if we claim that all physics *is* computation, when the latter is really just a model of a very peculiar human activity (to calculate by rote with pen and paper). Computation, in this sense, has much more to do with how humans try to simulate and interpret reality, rather than being real in the same sense that physical observables are.

So, you may wonder: is it not hypocritical then to rely on evolutionary narratives and a rather abstract and speculative model of a living system for our perspectivist epistemology? Is this not committing the same map-and-territory fallacy?

I think not. After all, as naturalist thinkers, we *want* our philosophy to be *informed* by the most up-to-date scientific theories. This is not problematic as long as I do not pick any specific scientific theory as the *foundation* for my theory of knowledge or reality. In the account that I present, evolution and autopoiesis play distinct, auxiliary roles: they provide the most plausible naturalistic explanations we currently have to ground knowledge in the experience of an evolved and limited living being. This is clearly not the same as claiming that the laws of physics (or computation) are *more* real than the experience from which such theories and concepts emerge. Instead, it simply acknowledges that science and philosophy must go together to yield the best grip on reality we can get — as human beings, in this particular place and time.

This is where Wimsatt comes back into our discussion with a crisp mission statement, saying that he too wants “to re-psychologize, re-socialize, and re-embed us in the world, where we reason about that world *as well as about how we interact with and reflect upon it.*” (Wimsatt,

2007, p.7, *my emphasis*). In contrast to the all-knowing, rational actors of neoclassical economics and foundationalist epistemology (idealizations that are *not* limited beings), we must give our biases and limitations — as documented by biology, neuroscience, psychology, and the social sciences — center stage. They are essential if we want to explain how science is *actually* done in practice. And here is that inescapable strange loop again: knowers must study *themselves* scientifically, as *objects*, if they are to understand knowledge in relation to themselves, as *subjects*.

Humans are prone to many biases, social ones, for instance: we suppress disagreements within our tribe while exaggerating them when it comes to our perceived nemeses. This creates pseudo-controversies, and impedes the free flow of ideas. Moreover, we are very good at overestimating our own capacities, and to overextend those ideas and theories we already know while neglecting potential alternatives. But not all our foibles are necessarily bad for science: consider, for example, that limited beings rarely go for an optimal problem-solving approach, as this usually requires excessive time, energy, and resources, or physical, cognitive, and technological capacities we do not have. Instead, we compromise and improvise, we oversimplify and idealize. This is a feature, not a bug: we rely on kluges and shortcuts to get anywhere at all. Otherwise, we'd still be designing our first experiment, or be contemplating that perfect model, without ever implementing any of it. We are only human after all.

A more technical term for “kluges and shortcuts” is *heuristics*. Like algorithms, heuristics are problem-solving strategies that can be formally defined as computations — ordered sequences of operations expressed through simple and unambiguous instructions. Yet, unlike algorithms, heuristics are not guaranteed to converge on a solution of the problem. They are rules of thumb, succeeding most of the time by returning answers in the right ballpark. Heuristics generally require less effort than an optimal algorithm, and can be tuned to the expected quality of the outcome. Economist and complexity scientist Herbert Simon (1955, 1969) calls it *satisficing* (a portmanteau of “satisfy” and “suffice”) in his account of *bounded rationality*, which examines how humans (over)simplify problems in light of incomplete knowledge.

Much of the skillful art of modeling lies in the choice of methods and systems that are not just adequate and informative for the question at hand, but also tractable and productive given our available resources. This amounts to transforming a hard problem into an intuitively related one that may not be exactly equivalent, but is much easier to tackle. It is how heuristics enable us to make any progress at all. The downside of this approach, obviously, is that it constantly introduces new sources of systematic error into scientific inquiry. We shall see in [section 5](#), however, that we can use even these errors as a source of insight.

The most prominent heuristic bias of our current science is *reductionism*. Wimsatt examines it in detail. In its widest sense, it includes any kind of analytic method or technique — theoretical and empirical — which decomposes an entity or system into its constituent (physical) parts and their interactions. This creates two major blind spots. First, it generally underestimates the influence of context. It takes for granted that an entity or system, and its parts, can be studied in perfect isolation, once partitioned away from the rest of the world. And second, it assumes that higher-level phenomena can be explained entirely by what is going on at a lower level.

Take *genetic determinism* in biology as an illustration of the kind of problem this creates. We like to dissect biological traits into underlying molecular genetic factors that contribute to their generation and hereditary transmission. The genomes that harbor these factors are themselves subcomponents of a living system that are deeply embedded in its overall organization. In fact, their operation and function can only be understood within this larger context and, yet, this is rarely done in biological practice these days. Instead, we insist on “bottoming-out” to the level of molecular mechanisms, we attribute a kind of agency to genes (saying that they “produce” or “make” traits, for example), and we use inappropriate metaphors like the “genetic program,” when genes do not “code” for anything but protein sequences, and are just as responsive to the cellular milieu as they are productive of it. To paraphrase biologist C. H. Waddington (1957): it is impossible to decide whether genomes instruct cells, or whether cells actively interpret genomes. What matters here are relations that are *not* captured by reductive explanations.

But this does not mean that Wimsatt is *against* reductionism. In fact, he praises it as an incredibly *useful* heuristic, and we will see why in the [next section](#). The danger lies not in applying it as a practical tool or method, but to mistake it for an accurate representation of reality — often the *only* acceptable representation. He calls this “*nothing-but-ism*.” Nothing-but-ists not only treat the world *as if* it were reducible (out of practical need), they see their reduced version of it *as reality* (a metaphysical worldview, to the exclusion of alternative views). The difference is crucial. Nothing-but-ism is popular and widespread, especially among researchers. Many of us are both intellectually and emotionally committed to it, not least because it gives us the illusion of simplicity, predictability, power, and control. But, thanks to Wimsatt, we realize why this view is hollow: it is a projection of our reductionist heuristics *onto* a complex world. Map and territory, yet again.

Where, then, do such effective but sometimes deceptive heuristics come from? And how do we choose what problems to apply them to? Wimsatt sees heuristics as the result of biological and cultural *evolutionary adaptation*: “[a] naturalistic worldview of the genesis and operation of functionally organized evolving systems is heuristics all the way down — as far down as entities or configurations of them are products of selection.” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 11). This seems

plausible, but leaves a number of important questions open. For instance, there is the *question of origin*: a living system must be at least minimally aligned with its environment to survive *before* it can be subjected to natural selection (Jaeger, 2024b). Thus, its heuristics may adapt but cannot originate through selection alone. And there is the *question of relevance*: how does a living being *frame* the problems to which its heuristics are applied? After all, we live in a world where most problems do not just appear to us, out of nowhere, in some well-defined format.

This is what statistician Leonard Savage (1954) calls a *large world*. It has nothing to do with size. Humans are indeed small and ephemeral compared to the extension and age of the universe, but this is not the point. Instead, “large” denotes a world in which objects, properties, relations, systems, and the problems associated with them are not objectively preconfigured before we experience them. They remain *indefinite* until our interaction. Therefore, they must be made explicit and precise *before* we can develop heuristics to tackle them. It’s not that the tree does not make a sound if it falls in the forest without anybody being there to hear it. But it is only noticed and *conceptualized* as a “tree” “making a sound” by “falling” in the “forest” through our recording of the event. The ability to do this depends, once again, on the unique characteristics of living (and in particular human) beings (Roli et al., 2022; Jaeger et al., 2024). How we pick out features of our perceived environment — among the indefinitely many possible alternatives — depends on our sensory capabilities, conceptual and cognitive tools, prior knowledge, and imagination, but also on what is relevant to us, our prioritized goals, in our particular situation. And what we pick out is crucial for our survival. Therefore, making sense of our world is as much about *judgment* and *creativity* as it is about problem solving (*i.e.*, *computation*). As I said before: you can only generate, evolve, and improve your heuristics if you can define the problems to which they are to be applied in the first place.

This view of limited beings in a large world has important and wide-reaching implications. For one, it presents a plausible argument for why our knowledge of the world is, and will probably always remain, *piecewise* and *approximate*. “Constrained fuzzy order” is the norm: “on our time and size scale, and for several orders of magnitude in each direction, it is exceptionless crisp precision that is the degenerate special case” (Wimsatt, 2007, p.33). In light of this, the prospect of a formal, universal theory of everything seems extremely remote — and no longer desirable: a quixotic quest for any limited intelligence; not the windmill we should chase.

This is a good thing. It means that we’d better abandon our hubristic and dangerous illusions of omniscience and omnipotence — the sooner the better. We are not in control or command of reality. But it does *not* mean that we cannot *make sense* of our experiences, our world, as human beings. Quite the contrary: we gain a kind of freedom that is essential for a meaningful life, an opening for creativity and exploration. The incomplete nature of our knowledge means

that the universe will always continue to surprise us. Even if the current laws of physics *would* tell us that the future is causally predetermined — which they do *not* — there would still be room for radical novelty, as our models and theories keep on evolving in ways we cannot possibly predict. And, yet, their evolution is not completely arbitrary either (contra Feyerabend). There *is* a “toolbox of science” in wide (though not universal) use, shaping how research progresses. And this research is revealing a causal structure of the universe that is exactly the kind of structure that a limited being like us can make sense of. Why this is not surprising — and not a self-fulfilling prophecy or the result of viciously circular reasoning — is the topic of the following sections.

2. Levels of organization: the kind of world we can exist and evolve in

"Ontological genocide was practiced upon whole classes of upper-level or 'derivative' entities in the name of elegance, and we were secure in the belief that one strayed irremediably into the realm of conceptual confusion and possible error the further one got from ontic fundamentalism." (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 193)

If you are a scientist, you may not know his name, but Willard Van Orman Quine is one of the most important analytic philosophers of the 20th century. He made an argument that still has a huge influence on how we do science today. Wimsatt’s somewhat flowery quote above is about that. Quine’s question was simple. He asked: *what is there?* His famous answer: *everything!* We have seen this kind of philosophy before: it makes perfect sense, but is also perfectly useless.

To be fair, Quine also has some more practical advice regarding our *ontological commitments* — what we should consider real. This advice *is* relevant to the working scientist: *keep it simple*, Quine says, and only accept those abstract entities as actually existing that are absolutely indispensable for your theories. He calls this minimalist approach *desert landscape ontology* (Quine, 1948, 1951). It is what Wimsatt calls out as “ontic fundamentalism.” Desert ontology is ideally suited for reductionism, and the Greek take on scientific theory. It engenders the “ontological genocide” that Wimsatt is lamenting. Only laws of physics were considered fundamental, and so it was mostly entities from the special sciences that got eliminated on Quine’s advice. And there was little resistance among philosophers or scientists against this conceptual massacre.

Wimsatt, somewhat whimsically, calls Quine’s advice “*Occam’s eraser*,” and argues that it is generally unsound for the kind of Babylonian science he envisions. Remember: Greek science is anchored in a small number of abstract and general laws and the concepts they require, while Babylonian science has much more networked support, based on concrete observations and local models, which requires a much richer and multilayered conceptual framework.

How to undo the ontological genocide? Choosing the best strategy depends very much on what kind of causal structure the world around us actually exhibits. What can we say about that?

Quite a lot, it turns out, even before we do any empirical science at all. We do this by asking: *what is the kind of universe a limited being like us can actually exist in?* What is the kind of causal structure which would enable us to survive and evolve? Without knowers, no knowledge, after all. This already excludes quite a lot of possibilities. Imagine a completely random universe (Fig. 1, top panel). It can produce patterns haphazardly, by chance, but no enduring regularities. Our internal models would have no predictive power and we could not anticipate anything. Surely, we would not last very long in such a world.

Fig 1: a multi-levelled world. Levels of organization are shown in waveform (middle), and contrasted to a purely random (top), and a strictly mechanistic world (bottom), in which no levels exist or everything can be reduced to a single fundamental level, respectively. See text for details. Inspired by Wimsatt (2007), Fig. 10.1 (pp. 224/5). Artwork by Marcus Neustetter.

On the other extreme, imagine a universe that is completely rigid and flat — a purely mechanical clockwork where the future is completely predetermined by the workings of a particular and limited set of “gears,” from the beginning to the end of time (Fig. 1B, bottom). As explained in the [previous section](#), life could not exist in this world either. Self-manufacture is not supported in such a horizontal, deterministic world. Moreover, there is no openness about

the future, and thus no true innovation in evolution. Taken together, this suggests that evolved life requires a universe somewhere in the middle (Fig. 1) — with enough indeterminacy for novelty and surprise, but also enough regularity and layered structure for survival and adaptation.

As good naturalists, of course, we are allowed to also consider the current state of our empirical science, which means that we can say quite a lot more about the structure of the world. For example, our observations tell us that all but the most elementary physical entities are made of parts, and most processes emerge from the interactions of various component subprocesses. The world has a fundamentally nested and hierarchical structure.

Once more, let's take a living system as our example: its *life cycle* involves all kinds of metabolic, physiological, developmental, and behavioral activities whose coherent and constructive interrelations are what enables it to survive, mature, and reproduce. At the same time, its body as an entity (if it is a multicellular organism) is constructed of smaller entities such as organs, tissues, cells, organelles, (macro)molecules, and atoms. As argued in the [previous section](#), these components (no matter whether we consider them as processes or objects) are co-constructing each other in a way so as to actively maintain and manufacture their own organization. This is how a living system keeps itself alive, and how it maintains its identity. Evidently, this kind of system has to be composed of multiple *levels of organization* (Fig. 1; Eronen & Brooks, 2024).

This is a core concept of Wimsatt's philosophy, and one that contrasts radically with earlier notions of levels (see, for example, Brooks, 2017): "levels of organization are a deep, non-arbitrary, and extremely important feature of the ontological architecture of our natural world, and almost certainly of any world which could produce, and be inhabited or understood by, intelligent beings." (Wimsatt, 2007, p.203). They are the "vertebrae" of "nature carved by its joints" (*ibid.*, p.64) — the simplest and most general large-scale structures for the organization of matter in the universe. We can discern levels in terms of their *compositional hierarchy*: higher-level entities or processes are composed of lower-level ones. This means there is often (but not always) a correlation with scale. Within themselves, levels tend to be constituted by entities that are of comparable size, are subject to similar forces, and therefore show similar dynamic behavior. These entities interact mainly with each other. This is why they "give an apparent rough closure over a range of phenomena and regularities" (*ibid.*, p.204), that is, the same explanatory strategies tend to apply to entities within a level. Or, even more abstractedly, Wimsatt defines levels to be "local maxima of regularity and predictability in the phase space of alternate modes of organization of matter" (*ibid.*, p.209). This explains why our scientific theories tend to trace levels and to describe the world "in strata."

Take, for example, the *atomic level*: it is composed of particles whose size and weight varies within a rather narrow range. Atoms are all around 100 picometers in diameter, and the ratio of the atomic weights of hydrogen and of Oganesson, the heaviest unstable element synthesized so far, is only about 1/300. Of course, we no longer consider atoms to be indivisible today. They are composed of more fundamental particles, such as protons, neutrons, and electrons, which exist at lower levels. In turn, atoms interact with each other by combining into molecules, salts, and metals, which constitute the next level up. The electromagnetic force is dominant at this level: it explains both the attraction of electrons and atomic nuclei, as well as the covalent and ionic bonds that constitute higher-level structures.

But not all levels are distinguished this cleanly. In fact, as Wimsatt notes, there is a tendency of higher levels to be less well defined. The entities that constitute them become increasingly heterogenous in terms of their composition, size, and behavior, and higher levels often overlap more than lower ones. As an example, consider the *cellular level* in biology: cells are extremely diverse in terms of their morphology, range in size from tiny mycoplasma bacteria a fraction of a micrometer in diameter to mycorrhizal mycelia that span several kilometers, and show all kinds of behaviors, from immobile plant or fungal cells to sophisticated unicellular predators with their incredibly rich and dynamic repertoire of actions. Also note how different cells interact with the molecular level of their surroundings in different ways: a small bacterium or protist constantly gets pummeled in random directions by the dance of single molecules in Brownian motion, while a large unicellular alga will be swaying softly in tune with the coherent convective flows in the water-based physical environment they both have in common.

I cannot emphasize enough that Wimsatt's level concept is not just an *epistemic tool* or a *doctrine* to structure our scientific knowledge and practice (although it is this as well, see Brooks, 2021b). Levels are very real and crucial *ontological features* of the world we live in, and a prerequisite for us to make sense of that world in the first place. Now, you may ask: how is this even possible? How can it be that entities at higher levels are entirely composed of lower-level ones, but still somehow have their own independent existence? Does this not contradict the principles of physics, in particular, the conservation of matter and energy? And you are right to ask these questions because the answers are not obvious. They require me to introduce three more Wimsattian key concepts.

Multiple-realizability is quite easy to understand: since any single higher-level entity or process is made of many lower-level ones, there is a higher number of possible micro-configurations than macro-configurations. This means that many micro-states must map to the same macro-state. The latter can be realized in multiple ways. In turn, this implies that many changes at the lower-level will not have any effect at the higher level. It becomes somewhat insulated

from lower-level happenings. What we need to understand, then, are not only changes at the lower level but also if and how they propagate upward. What matters are the relations *between* levels. Otherwise we won't know which lower-level events affect higher-level dynamics, and which ones do not. This conveys a basic sense in which higher levels have an autonomous existence: their dynamics cannot be understood completely if we only focus on the lower ones.

But this is not the only way in which levels can be autonomous. Higher-level processes also tend to be *slower* than those at lower ones. This is mainly because causal effects take longer to propagate at larger scales, which implies that higher-level entities may be stable, while their lower-level components are constantly coming and going. This is called *dynamic autonomy*. Again, think of a living being: the cells of your body constantly renew and replace themselves, while the molecules constituting those cells get generated, taken up, recombined, transformed, secreted, and decay at an even higher rate. And yet, you and your cells retain your separate identities through all of this lower-level turnover and turmoil. Therefore, higher-level organization can be preserved in a way that is independent of lower-level events, at least to some degree. Again, this means that many, if not most, micro-level changes make no difference at the higher level, and we must understand that level in terms of its own organization.

Finally, building on the above, we can look at *emergent properties* and *behaviors* that only manifest at higher levels. Again, this has to do with how components are organized to constitute an entity or a system. Take, for example, a multi-component oscillator such as a (maladjusted) thermostat with a delay between sensor, controller, and effector (the heating unit). Instead of keeping the temperature constant, this thermostat will fluctuate around its setpoint. Evidently, none of the components drive the oscillations on their own. What is required is a particular dynamic mode of interaction between the lot of them. The property "is an oscillator" or the activity "to oscillate" do not reside in any individual part of the system. They are emergent phenomena in that they only exist at the level of the entire thermostat. This kind of emergence does not reflect a lack of knowledge. Instead, individual components are simply the wrong level of organization at which to explain the oscillation. This is what Wimsatt calls *non-aggregativity*. It may not be the most elegant term, but it is extremely useful for explaining that emergence is literally *everywhere* and there is no mystery to it at all. Non-aggregativity is a form of *synchronic emergence*, because parts and emergent phenomena co-exist in parallel, at the same time.

For a proper definition of non-aggregativity, let us look at its opposite — *aggregativity* — and why it is so rare in nature. It is related to the idea of an extensive property in physics, a property that is additive for subsystems. More precisely, to be an aggregate, a higher-level property, object, or system needs to meet the following four conditions: it must remain invariant, or at

least scale in a regular manner, (1) when we rearrange or interchange parts (with other equivalent parts), (2) when we disassemble and reassemble parts, and (3) when we add or subtract parts. Finally, (4) there cannot be any cooperative or inhibitory interactions between parts, because they lead to irregular (nonlinear) responses. Almost no phenomena we observe really conform to all of these conditions. Wimsatt mentions mass as the only true aggregative property of objects. He also lists systems in which energy, momentum, or charge are conserved as examples. A surprising exception, in contrast, is volume: adding salt to water often *contracts* its volume. Thus, even volume is a *non*-aggregative property! Similarly, the oscillator above is a quintessentially non-aggregative system. If you remove any part or interaction, the oscillation disappears completely. In other cases, aggregativity is only approximate, as for the conserved systems above, because no object or process is truly isolated from the rest of the universe. Even here, complete conservation and thus true aggregativity are mere idealizations.

The bottom line is: *our multi-levelled world is decidedly non-aggregative in most of its aspects*. This is not just speculation: it is a fact we know with high confidence based on empirical investigations. Emergent properties, entities, and behaviors are here to stay — ontological genocide undone! Wimsatt, contra Quine's desert, calls this *the ontology of the tropical rainforest*. We live not only in a large, but also lush, dynamic, and irreducibly multilayered world. And, yet, we tend to assume that aggregativity is the norm. This is just plain wrong if taken as a worldview. But in practice it is not as unreasonable as it seems: in many cases, the assumption of aggregativity *will* work as a tractable heuristic — often, in fact, the only tractable heuristic. And this is precisely *because* the world is composed of levels, even if they may be non-aggregative in nature.

This seems counterintuitive, even paradoxical. Luckily, our example of the oscillator may help to resolve the conundrum. Is it really surprising that we *can* explain the oscillatory behavior in terms of the interrelations between sensor, controller, and effector unit? How else would you, as a scientist, explain it analytically? We need to decompose the system somehow to understand it in causal terms. And, yet, the oscillatory behavior still only emerges at the higher level of the system. There is no contradiction: even if we *do* manage to *explain* higher-level behavior through analytical reduction, this does not *explain* the higher level *away*. Non-aggregativity tells us why most phenomena in the world *are* emergent and, at the same time, why reductionist explanations still *do* work for us. If we are careful not to forget that they are idealizations, that is, which we all too often do. More on this tricky problem in [section 4](#).

For now, let me just reemphasize this surprising insight: *there is no inconsistency in using reductionism as a method* (all scientific analysis requires it to some degree) *and holding an emergentist view of the world at the same time*. Just don't be that nothing-but-ist! I told you

before: nothing-but-ism is an inappropriate and irresponsible stance for a limited being in a large and layered world, and the pervasive non-aggregativity between levels is the reason why.

An interesting conclusion we can draw is this: if levels of organization have an autonomous existence, as Wimsatt argues, then there is *no preferred level* to which we should target our explanations anymore. Entities at all levels can be equally real. As he remarks: “[t]here should be more ways of interacting with a spouse than with a quark!” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 223). We will further explore in the [next section](#) what this implies. For now, let me just remind you how much we are still stuck on “bottoming-out” all across the special sciences, as we have seen in the example of genetic determinism. Mind you: there is nothing wrong with explaining something in terms of its parts and their interactions. In fact, it is good scientific practice, especially if we cannot find an explanation at the same level. But to greedily demand that *all* explanations must be rooted in some fundamental level is more likely to lose the forest for the trees than to produce robust and useful insights at the appropriate level of organization.

Of course, the situation is still more complex than the tidy picture I have drawn. For one, there is the issue of how levels themselves emerge *over time*. Consider the *emergence of chemistry* through nucleosynthesis and recombination in cosmology, the *origin of life* (and thus the cellular level) as well as *multicellularity* in biology, or the *cultural evolution* of societies and technologies within the human lineage. Even though all of these originations involve plenty of non-aggregativity, they represent an entirely different kind of *diachronic emergence* where new forms of higher-level organization arise (over time) from lower-level ones in radically unpredictable ways. Moreover, there is the issue of *downward causation*: constraints from higher levels can change the behavior of entities at lower levels. Again, there is no magic here, but both of the above issues introduce further challenges for reductionist explanation.

In addition, I already mentioned that levels are often not clearly separable from one another (*cf.* the cellular level). Even worse, some parts of our reality seem to lack distinguishable levels altogether (see [sections 4](#) and [7](#)). This has led some critics to dismiss the level concept as useless, even misleading. These criticisms are discussed elsewhere (see [\[refs\]](#), this issue). For our present purposes, it suffices to say that the subdivision of reality into levels may be messy and partial (Wimsatt, 2021), but this neither implies that the world isn’t multi-levelled at all, nor that the concept of levels of organization isn’t useful (or even required) for doing scientific research (see, Brooks, 2017; Brooks & Eronen, 2018; Brooks, 2021a,b). Of course, this is all in accordance with Wimsatt’s down-to-earth approach: the levels concept may be fragmentary in that it gets defined in context-dependent ways that may not add up to a single consistent big picture, but it is nonetheless *useful* as a heuristic tool empowering our scientific practice.

To summarize: levels of organization are major and irreducible *ontological features* of a world where limited beings like us can exist and evolve. This is also the kind of world that we can get to know, at least approximately and piecemeal, through reductionist heuristics. One follows from the other without descending into vicious circularity, as we'll see in the following sections.

3. Beyond certainty: scientific knowledge is robust (and useful)

"Things are robust if they are accessible (detectable, measurable, derivable, definable, producible, or the like) in a variety of independent ways." (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 196)

If you have properly digested what we have discussed so far, you may feel a bit disoriented by now — like you are losing your conceptual footing. This is perfectly normal. Or, at least, this is how I felt when reading Wimsatt for the first time. I started to wonder: if he is right, and there is no certainty anchored in universal laws at a fundamental level of reality, *how can we trust any knowledge at all?* Are we not on a slippery slope towards a radical skepticism about science?

In this situation, the most important thing is *not* to make a hasty retreat back into illusory certainties. But neither is it okay to fall into fashionable postmodern relativism and ennui. It is not true that anything goes, and nothing works anymore. Quite the contrary: our probability of failure may never reach zero, but it is still in our hands to lower it considerably. We can still get a *good enough* grip on reality. And this is not despite but *because* of scientific knowledge remaining fallible and always open to revision. For limited beings in a large and multi-levelled world, global metaphysical realism is not, and has never been, a realistic goal anyway. Let's face it: we are nowhere near approaching objective truth or reality. If we are honest, we have no idea what this would even mean. Yet, we need not abandon realism altogether. As researchers, we can still judge our knowledge by its *relative reliability*. we just need a criterion that tells us whether it is *trustworthy enough* for us to base our further explorations of the world on it. This is how we generate *adaptive knowledge*. And science is and remains the best way for us to do this.

What is this criterion? Wimsatt calls it *robustness*. It is rooted in the *evolutionary epistemology* of social scientist Donald T. Campbell, (1974; see also Bradie & Harms, 2023) and his concept of *multiple determination* (not the same as *multiple realizability*). The idea is straightforward. It is captured by the quote at the beginning of [this section](#): phenomena and events we experience (as well as their properties) should be considered real insofar as they are *accessible* to us in a variety of independent ways.

Let's consider concrete examples. Robust *entities, events, relationships, and properties* are directly *observed* through distinct sensory modalities, or *detected* via different technological devices. Our visual perception of the brightness of a flame goes together with the sensation of pain after touching it. We always hear the thunder after we see the lightning. In astronomy, we match sources of radio waves and high-energy rays — such as quasars, active galactic nuclei, pulsars, supernovas, and the like — with their emissions in the visible and infrared spectrum. In biology, we detect and characterize cellular structures by light *and* electron microscopy. Or we fail to do so, as in the famous case of the bacterial mesosome, which turned out to be an artefact of how frozen samples were prepared for cryo-electron micrographs. Mesosomes, it turns out, are *not* robust (Culp, 1994, 1995). Consequently, they are no longer considered real by most biologists.

Similarly, *quantities* are robust if they can be *measured and ordered* by distinct experimental means. Thermometers, for instance, come in all kinds of varieties, based on different materials, or even radiometric methods. This is why we consider temperature a real property of the world, even though it is only a statistical concept if considered at the molecular level. Similarly, distinct types of scales detect weight, various containers measure volume, and so on.

Mathematical and other *abstract concepts* are robust if they can be *defined or derived*, in various ways, from different assumptions, axioms, or models. Self-referential paradoxes, like Russell's paradox, occur across mathematical disciplines, meaning they are probably here to stay. In physics, abstract entities like the electron and its properties show up in all kinds of theories, which are highly robust themselves. Thus, most physicists treat the electron as a real object. Likewise, genes in biology are used not only to explain heredity, but also the regulatory properties of cellular and developmental processes. Even though genes started out as purely abstract entities, and their definition changed quite radically from classical to molecular genetics (without these definitions mapping precisely onto each other), we assume genes to be real, because they do useful work in explaining so many different biological phenomena, and are central inferential nodes in the conceptual frameworks used to justify these explanations.

Moreover, *effects* and *artifacts* — including elements of human knowledge, like *insights* — are robust if they can be *generated* by independent means of production. Different human cultures have built similar tools, weapons, and accessories by different methods and from different materials, which means these designs are robust. Think stone versus steel axe, or disposable tableware: a plastic knife is still a knife. By analogy, robust insights can be produced in various ways. For instance, perturbing a complex system almost always generates unwanted side effects, no matter what kind of intervention is applied. Therefore, these effects — and the insight we should draw from their frequent occurrence — are highly robust. In the same sense,

our evolved heuristics themselves can be robust. Reductionism, as we have seen in the [previous section](#), is an example of a robust heuristic, widely used across many scientific disciplines.

Finally, let me remind you that *levels of organization* are one of the most robust features of our world, not least because phenomena at higher levels behave in a robust way: they are multiply realized by lower-level entities, as well as dynamically autonomous from, and emergent upon, those entities. Remember that you persist as an individual, while the molecules and cells of your body constantly turn over. Complementary to this, we also consider a phenomenon robust if it is captured by matching descriptions at *different* levels of organization. In evolutionary biology, the phenotypic change of a trait at the cellular, tissue, or organismic level correlates with genetic changes at the molecular level. Biologists call this the *genotype-phenotype map*. Or, consider rational-choice modeling as a *failure* of this kind of robustness: the (not generally rational) behavior of individual humans influences the behavior of the economy as a whole in ways that are *not* captured or predicted by these models.

From these examples, it should be clear that “all the variants and uses of robustness have a common theme in the distinguishing of the real from the illusory; the reliable from the unreliable; the objective from the subjective; the object of focus from artifacts of perspective; and, in general, that which is regarded as ontologically and epistemologically trustworthy and valuable from that which is unreliable, ungeneralizable, worthless, and fleeting” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 46). This criterion for the soundness of our knowledge, Wimsatt argues, is the best any limited intelligence could hope for. And it is both consistent and actually applicable in practice, unlike any of the foundationalist “God’s-eye” theories of knowledge we reviewed in [section 1](#).

Wimsatt’s robustness criterion cuts through a long-running philosophical debate between *realists* and *instrumentalists* (sometimes called “*anti-realists*,” which misleadingly suggests they do not believe in reality; see Ladyman, 2002, for an accessible introduction). It exposes the false dichotomy around which this debate is structured. In brief, the discussion concerns the question whether abstract concepts in science (electrons or genes, for example) represent real entities or properties, or whether we should consider such concepts in a purely instrumental manner, as tools for making inferences or predictions about entities and properties that can actually be observed. Wimsatt tells us: it depends. Each such concept should be considered real insofar as it is robust. And, in each case, we should leave it to the scientists to make the final judgment. There is no general answer, as robustness applies to individual entities and properties and also changes as scientific knowledge evolves (*cf.* [section 6](#)). Thus, whether something is real or not is not exclusively a philosophical matter, but is deeply rooted in scientific practice. And the debate, as originally posed, cannot be resolved since it lacks nuance (and misses the point).

This brings us to an important caveat: remember that Wimsatt is concerned with anchoring *scientific* knowledge in reality. He wants an actionable criterion for what is “objective,” in the specific sense that it constitutes generalizable knowledge about the world that we can apply as widely as possible. Yet, as discussed in [section 1](#), there is a strange loop between the subjective knower and the objective known: they are intimately entangled in the sense that all knowledge is ultimately derived from the (non-robust) subjective experience of a knower. Wimsatt would not deny that. Quite the contrary: after all, he is explicitly developing a theory of knowledge for limited beings. Even though he does not say this explicitly, we must consider our subjective experiences and feelings real in a different, more basic, sense — that of being the actual experiences of an actual knower. What robustness does is explain how we go from one to the other. It says that we should not uncritically trust our intuitive feelings, as we may be mistaken or deluded. Robustness is what allows us to overcome error and self-deception. It is what makes scientific knowledge *more reliable* than other ways of knowing.

In summary, robust phenomena and properties — because of their multiple connections and applicable descriptions — tend to be (1) more easily accessible, (2) less prone to illusion, (3) more explanatorily powerful, and (4) more likely to yield accurate predictions, than non-robust ones. This is what makes robustness such a good criterion for trustworthy scientific knowledge.

Yet, we must be careful, because there is such a thing as *illusory robustness*. It occurs when the methods we use to access an apparently robust phenomenon are not truly independent. Wimsatt illustrates this with the debate about group-level selection in evolution during the 1970s. In this debate, different theoretical models were used to show that group selection would only apply under very unlikely circumstances. Unfortunately, all of these models assumed that the group is nothing but an aggregate of individuals when, in fact, group-level interactions can alter the selective pressures an individual is exposed to. Thus, all models shared a false simplifying assumption that turned out to be highly significant for the inferences drawn from them. Here, the robustness of the insight was itself not real because the means of derivation were not independent, and the debate about group selection still rages on today.

Wimsatt suggests we use *robustness analysis* to prevent such mistakes (see also Levins, 1966). It proceeds in four steps: (1) we analyze the various ways in which a robust phenomenon or property was accessed or produced, and check whether they are methodologically sound, and truly independent of each other; (2) we identify insights and results that remain the same between different approaches; (3) we determine the scope of methods across which this invariance holds, and the conditions upon which it depends; and (4) we also examine relevant failures of invariance — where and why does it break down? The group selection debate failed the first step already, which is not very informative beyond showing us that the conclusions

were *not* robust. In other contexts, failure occurs at later steps. This means we can not only learn about the soundness of our methods and models from this type of *means-end analysis*, but also about how trustworthy and generalizable our insights and results really are. Imagine how the quality of our research would improve if robustness analysis were made standard scientific practice. To achieve this, we must make scientists think more about philosophy again.

To end this section, I briefly want to mention that robustness is only one of many ways by which we can establish the worth of scientific knowledge. Other perspectivist criteria are possible, such as Michela Massimi's (2016, 2022) notion of *perspectival truth*. Like robustness, it is based on identifying invariants across different perspectives. But, unlike Wimsatt, it retains the idea that knowledge can be "true" (not just trustworthy). To do this, it requires a stronger concept of "reality" than the one used here — one made up of specific "states of affairs" that are independent of the knower. Which one you prefer is a matter of metaphysical debate with little bearing on scientific practice, so we will leave it to the philosophers. More relevant, in practice, is a modern form of *pragmatist philosophy* that sees *usefulness* as the most important criterion for the quality of scientific knowledge. Hasok Chang (2022), for example, judges insights by how much they enable us to *act coherently* in the world. I find this view quite appealing, and complementary to Wimsatt's. Both go well together: robustness lays the ground for *why* knowledge can be useful in Chang's sense.

4. Perspectives: piecewise approximations to a complex reality

"[P]erspectives [are] intriguingly quasi-subjective (or at least observer, technique or technology-relative) cuts on the phenomena characteristic of a system, which needn't be bound to given levels." (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 222)

I ended [section 2](#) by mentioning that the subdivision of our world into levels of organization is messy and partial. "[W]hen neat compositional relations break down, levels become less useful as ways of characterizing the organization of systems" (Wimsatt, 2007, pp. 221/2). This mainly happens at higher levels, because they tend to be more heterogeneous and overlap more. Living organisms are examples of systems whose organization *must* span multiple levels for them to be self-manufacturing (see [sections 1](#) and [2](#)). We can still describe such a system through the use of various local models, but they no longer neatly map onto single levels, reduce phenomena from one level to another, or match up with each other as part of a broad, overarching theory. This is why it is so difficult to find general laws in the life and social sciences: such laws rarely match aspects of reality where levels cannot be clearly discerned.

When levels break down, *perspectives* come in. This concept — defined in the quote at the beginning of [this section](#) — is one of Wimsatt's most difficult ones. At the same time, it is also crucial for understanding his philosophy and its importance for science.

A Wimsattian perspective is not just a subjective “point of view,” but a “quasi-subjective” and “strange” object: an “ontological structure” that we can use as a tool — more specifically, as a replacement for “level” — when we need to make “cuts on phenomena” that are not “bound to given levels” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 222). I interpret this as saying that a perspective arises from the *interaction* of a limited being with a complex world that is not always perfectly layered. Sometimes — quite often, in fact — we need to cut across levels. And, as is the case for levels, we can consider a multi-level perspective real if it is the robust outcome of various independent interactions between the knower and what is to be known.

Perspectives, on this account, are neither purely subjective nor objective, but their nature lies somewhere in between. We could say they are *transjective*, bridging both categories (Jaeger et al., 2024). So are levels of organization, by the way. They too are neither purely ontological (“out there in the world”), nor purely epistemic (“belonging to our domain of knowledge”), but are a basic feature of how we limited beings come to know a world that has a specific kind of causal structure (see [sections 1](#) and [2](#)). This intimate intermingling of subjective and objective, of ontological and epistemic, is characteristic of perspectival realism. It is a direct consequence of the strange loop that makes us simultaneously the subject and object of our knowledge.

Perspectives are hard to pin down precisely, because they encompass “a diverse category of things which [...] differ substantially [...] in terms of their relative ‘objectivity’” (Wimsatt, 2007, pp. 227). Each perspective focuses on a specific set of variables which are used to explain phenomena that are salient and appear related to an observer interacting with a system. None of these sets give a complete account of *all* aspects of the system, and we may apply *multiple perspectives* to the same system, each capturing different types of phenomena. This is the “quasi-subjective” part: how we delimit a perspective — and how we formalize it into a model — always depends on what the knower desires to know. Such perspectives are not, in general, part of a simple compositional order with regard to each other (like higher levels made out of entities at lower levels). Yet, partial hierarchical decomposition may still be possible to some degree. In this sense, levels can be seen as particularly neatly layered kinds of perspectives.

All of this should sound familiar to anyone involved in experimental work or modeling in the special sciences. To design an experiment, or to formulate a model, we first decompose the system under study by picking a set of variables to concentrate on. How we choose these variables is not arbitrary, but also not guided by first principles. It is a skillful art that requires practical experience and schooled intuition. And it depends radically on the current context.

Genetic analysis is an example of a very robust perspective in biology. We traditionally focus on genes and their role in the generation of phenotypic traits — the color of your eyes, say, or

your ability to metabolize alcohol, or the shape and function of your brain. We identify relevant system components and their interactions through *functional decomposition*. For instance, we may screen for candidate genes by mutating them and checking if and how the trait is affected. We also simulate interactions among genes — gene regulatory networks — using mathematical and computational models. Ideally, this enables us to localize the function of each gene to a specific physical structure or regulatory process. Most of the time, however, it tends to yield ambiguous results: the same gene may be involved in the formation of multiple traits, and genes interact in non-aggregative ways that often make it difficult to interpret mutant phenotypes. This kind of *failure of functional localization* is very common in reductionist science, as soon as we leave those domains of reality that are cleanly layered — which are the domains of the very small and the very large that fundamental physics focuses on.

Similar *perspectival approaches* are applied across the special sciences — from biology to neuroscience to psychology to the social sciences. The decomposition we choose always depends on our research question. And, usually, we end up with a local model that only explains specific phenomena in a narrow domain. But, if we're lucky, some amount of generalization is possible when our model overlaps with other local models in terms of its variables and the phenomena they explain. And sometimes, surprisingly, overlap occurs across entirely unrelated domains. Gene regulatory network models, for instance, are historically derived from spin-glass models of interacting ferromagnets (Knuutila & Loettgers, 2014, 2016, 2023) — even though these systems differ radically in scale and material composition. The discovery of such overlaps seems to be contingent: we know of no general principles that would allow us to predict them. This paints a picture of a truly Babylonian (bottom-up) science that is driven by extension of local models, not the Greek (top-down) derivation of local models from general laws.

Wimsatt calls this bottom-up approach *piecewise (or piecemeal) engineering*, a term inspired by Herbert Simon (1969). In those domains where levels break down and perspectives are the norm, we should not expect models to add up or generalize in any straightforward manner. Still, we can learn a lot by examining how local models perform, where they fail, and how they relate to each other. Instead of reveling in physics envy, Wimsatt suggests, we should “make messiness and ontological profligacy fascinating, attractive, and even respectable” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 322). But, he also warns that “not any mess will do” and “many exemplars of ‘the new messiness’ do not fare well” (*ibid.*). What we need is neither anything-goes relativism nor more intricate abstract theorizing, but an empirically grounded understanding of how science actually produces robust insight in practice. I'll come back to this in the [next section](#).

In the meantime, it should be evident that we *need* multiple perspectives, based on distinct decompositions, to describe certain systems. For Wimsatt, such multiplicity defines a *complex system*. This idea, originally introduced by theoretical biologist Stuart Kauffman (1971), can be a little counterintuitive at first. Traditionally, we define *complexity* in terms of “objective” properties of a system — some combination of the number of heterogeneous parts, nonlinear interactions, feedback, multi-level organization, spontaneous emergent order, and/or the lack of centralized control (*cf.* Ladyman *et al.*, 2013). Wimsatt’s notion of complexity is radically different: it is *transjective*, determined by how many distinct decompositions are required to capture all the observed phenomena, and to what degree we fail to match them to each other.

To be precise, Wimsatt introduces two concepts. The first, *descriptive complexity*, looks at the boundaries of system components that are generated by distinct decompositions. If these boundaries coincide, then the system is simple. Think of a piece of basalt. We can crush it into smaller pieces with roughly constant chemical composition, crystalline form, density, tensile strength, and electrical or thermal conductivity. All these aspects can be decomposed in the same way. Therefore, basalt is descriptively simple (Fig. 2, left). In contrast, we may decompose a multicellular organism physically, into its segments and organs, or component cells and molecules, or we decompose it functionally, into different traits or cell types. Each cell type, in turn, activates distinct, characteristic sets of biochemical pathways. The boundaries created by these various decompositions do *not* coincide at all. Each trait, for example, is made up of a very particular arrangement of cells and molecules, which can also contribute to other traits but in different configurations. An organism, therefore, is descriptively complex (Fig. 2, right).

Fig 2: Simple vs. complex. In a simple system, like a piece of basalt rock (left), different decompositions map onto each other in a straightforward manner. In a complex system, like an ant (right), modular components generated by different decompositions relate in intricate ways (interactional complexity), and the boundaries of these components do not coincide across decompositions (descriptive complexity). See text for details. Inspired by Wimsatt (2007), Fig. 9.1 (p. 183). Artwork by Marcus Neustetter.

Wimsatt's second concept is *interactional complexity*, which assesses a system's *modularity*— or *near-decomposability*, to use Herbert Simon's (1962) term. It does this by measuring the fraction of interactions that occur *between* versus those that occur *within* components across distinct decompositions (again, see Fig. 2). Evolved systems, in particular, are often interactionally complex. Think again of the fact that most genes influence many traits in an organism. This is *not* how an engineer would have built such a system. Most designed human artifacts, however complicated, are interactionally simple. My smartphone, for example, is made of modules that can each be reordered and replaced by me, a user without any engineering skills. Physical and functional modules coincide. My smartphone is a pretty sophisticated piece of technology, and yet it is interactionally simple. A complex system *sensu* Wimsatt, in contrast, combines descriptive *and* interactional complexity. This category includes all living systems, as well as the ecosystems, organizations, or societies that contain them.

But why, you may ask, would we want to define complexity in this way? Is it really necessary to introduce the skillful and subjective aspect of choosing a decomposition into the definition? Is the traditional, “objective” concept not more useful and more robust? In fact, it is not. Its meaning is notoriously vague because nobody can agree on what criteria to include, and where to place the cut-off that separates complex from simple systems. Wimsattian complexity does not really address the latter problem. Only very few systems are truly aggregative (see [section 2](#)), and varying degrees of non-aggregativity mean that distinct decompositions yield different components. The cut-off problem is still there, but at least Wimsatt’s notion provides clear criteria for what counts as complex. And it provides a new explanation for why we always get unexpected side effects when intervening on a complex system (see [section 3](#)): there are always variables we have *not* considered in our particular set of decompositions.

In addition, it reveals an interesting bias of our reductionist heuristics, which stems from the fact that we tend to prefer decompositions that lead to *less* complexity in our *descriptions*. Instead of choosing the most robust approach, we are a bit lazy, cognitively speaking, and often ignore discrepancies and inconsistencies in our models and theories in favor of a clean and simple explanation. Even though convincing at first sight, this is not really cutting nature by its joints. Genes on their own do *not* produce traits, or program our growth and behavior, and they are *not* the only units of selection in evolution. Similarly, social dynamics are *not* reducible to the rational behavior of individuals. We know all that, and there is plenty of evidence to support it. Yet, nothing-but-ism lives on because it is convenient and makes the world look like a much more manageable place than it really is.

This is how Wimsattian complexity leads to rich insights into how we interact with the world, which cannot be had with traditional concepts. The sad truth is that there is almost never a simple one-to-one mapping between physical structures and functional components in a complex system. And pretty much every natural system is complex, or is embedded in a complex context. Think of our attempts to assign brain functions to specific neural structures, which is notoriously hard, and may not even be the right thing to do. This is another *functional localization failure*. It does not imply that function isn’t physical, or that we should give up correlating structure and function altogether. It just means that we ought to remember that our reductionist heuristics are idealizations — primitive maps, not accurate representations of the territory. What’s worse: this oversimplification is *deliberate*. Our models are false *by design*. In the next section, I’ll examine why this is not as terrible as it sounds, since false models are surprisingly *useful* for us to gain true(r) insights about the world.

5. Truer insights from false models: the metabolism of errors

"[M]ost writers [...] ignore the role that false models can have in improving our descriptions and explanations of the world. [...] While normally treated as a handicap, the falsity of scientific models is in fact often essential to this role."

(Wimsatt, 2007, p. 94)

How are our models false? And how can this be a good thing? The take-home message of this short section is simple: every scientific model is abstracted, incomplete, approximate, biased, and idealized, yet, it is exactly this imperfect nature that makes such models effective tools for our explorations of the world. Scientists, like all human beings, learn most from their mistakes.

Here, Wimsatt specifically considers both mathematical and causal models, the latter usually in the form of mechanistic explanations. There are many ways in which such models can be false:

1. They apply to a *limited domain*, and are false if applied to phenomena outside that domain. Simple genetic models applied to complex or environmentally sensitive traits come to mind.
2. They are *idealized*: what they represent never occurs in nature. Think of point masses in physics, or infinite and continuous population sizes in population genetics.
3. They are *incomplete*, leaving out variables that are causally relevant under certain circumstances. As an example, remember that reductionist heuristics generally neglect the influence of the environment, as well as interactions with other systems.
4. This can lead to a *misrepresentation of interactions* — spurious correlations (like that between storks and babies in Germany), or apparent independence between variables.
5. Models can be completely *wrong-headed* — containing incorrect interactions, and objects (or their properties) that don't exist. Rational-choice models in economics are an example.
6. They can be *phenomenological* in nature, simply describing observations without making any claims to the reality of their variables and interactions. Many statistical models used for curve-fitting are of this type.
7. Some models *fail to describe or predict the data*, but it is not known which of (1–6) apply.

Note that not every false model provides a path to better insights. Some of these failures are more informative than others. (5) and (7) are clearly problematic, and provide little useful purchase: "[s]ome models are so wrong, or their flaws are so difficult to analyze, that we are better off looking elsewhere" (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 103). (6) may be good for prediction, but usually fails at improving our understanding (but see below). In contrast, we can definitely work with (1–4): these models help us ask new questions, enable us to detect or estimate relevant variables that are not yet included (but may have implicitly shaped our formulations), and allow us to understand more realistic and complicated models that may be much less tractable. For this to succeed, our models must be formulated in a way that allows us to localize their errors,

that is, “to attribute them to some parts, aspects, assumptions, or subcomponents of the model” (*ibid.*). This is what *piecewise engineering* is all about (see the [previous section](#)).

If these conditions are met, then we can productively *metabolize our errors* by learning from false models in search of better (but still false) ones. Wimsatt (2007, p. 104ff) lists no less than twelve ways in which this can happen. Let us look at the most important ones.

A fairly obvious use of a false model is as a *starting point* for a series of increasingly complex and realistic models. The Lotka-Volterra equations describing predator-prey dynamics, for instance, grossly oversimplify the underlying interactions, but laid the foundation for the whole field of theoretical ecology (as recounted in Kingsland, 1995). Similarly, a *limiting model* is simplified such that it only applies under unrealistic circumstances, but provides bounds for more realistic models that are difficult to handle. Think of the ideal gas law — with its point masses and missing molecular collisions — compared to more realistic van der Waals gases — where molecules have spatial extension and do collide with each other (*cf.* Atkins et al., 2022). *Null models* are another related example of the use of false models, in this case as a reference standard to evaluate claims about variables they do *not* include, and to recognize and remove effects that may mask and confuse those we actually want to analyze. The Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium is a well-known case: it provides a reference distribution of alleles in an idealized population in the absence of confounding factors such as natural selection or genetic drift (see, for example, Hartl & Clark, 2007).

A different use of false models that can be informative is to explore *counterfactual scenarios*, especially in systems where optimal design or adaptation are important. Many evolutionary simulation studies work this way. Their main aim is not only to understand how evolution actually happened, but how it could have happened if things had gone differently. This allows us to sample the entire space of possibilities of a system — in theory at least.

Even purely *phenomenological models* can be useful. They allow us to characterize the form of relationships between observables — is the interaction linear or exponential, for example — which may lead to new predictions, and suggests possible mechanistic models to explain them.

Often, false models are not aimed at matching or predicting empirical observations at all. Instead, they are used to aid our thinking. So-called *toy models* provide a simple arena for probing questions about complex issues: they allow us to play around with alternative ways of thinking about some concept or problem, and to assess their basic logical consistency as a proof of principle. The Daisyworld model by Watson & Lovelock (1983) is a famous example: it showed that local ecological interactions can lead to global homeostatic regulation on an earth-like planet, without including any realistic representation of the actual biosphere.

But by far the most important use of false models is *to compare them*. In this way, we learn which insights hold across models, and which depend on specific underlying assumptions. This, in turn, tells us which assumptions are relevant to our conclusions, and which ones we can do without. Moreover, comparative analysis reveals which parts and interactions in a model are truly required for a certain outcome, and which ones are replaceable or redundant add-ons. Finally, model comparisons reveal whether our failures are random, or whether they are biased in certain directions. Systematic errors are the footprint of heuristics at work. By understanding them we can identify the shortcomings of our methods, and work towards better models that will be false in more interesting ways. It sounds paradoxical, but a perfect model is a dead end; false models are really what we need for our knowledge to evolve and adapt! Once you appreciate that, you will see the models used in your field in an entirely different light.

6. Knowledge evolves: conceptual engineering and generative entrenchment

"Rebuilding foundations after we have already erected an edifice on them is demanding and dangerous work. [...] This is why evolution proceeds mostly via a sequence of layered kluges." (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 137)

I've shown in the last [two sections](#) how the special sciences proceed by *piecewise engineering*, extending local models where possible while localizing their biases, limitations, and failures. Another central aspect of this kind of engineering is *exaptation* (Gould & Vrba, 1982): models that were originally formulated to attain one goal are repurposed to achieve another. The exaptation of gene networks from spin-glass models provides a good example (*cf.* [section 4](#)).

These bottom-up processes of perspectival knowledge production are radically unpredictable, historically contingent, and heavily dependent on context. Still, this doesn't mean that anything goes, as Feyerabend claimed (see [section 1](#)), and that we can say nothing at all about the ways by which scientific knowledge evolves.

For one, we can ask: why do certain insights persist through time while others fail to do so? We've already encountered one way by which this can happen in [section 3](#). *Robust* insights are reliable — resistant to failure — and so tend to endure. However, robustness may not only increase but also diminish as contrary evidence comes to light. And some insights may lack robustness to begin with, but are still difficult to change because tinkering with them would lead to the collapse of other structures that have been built upon them.

This is why scientists rarely work on the foundations of their fields (while foundations are pretty much all that philosophers think about): "[t]he more fundamental a proposed scientific change (or change of any other sort!), the broader its effect would be, and consequently, the less chance that it would work. So if adopted, the more work it would make for other

practitioners, changing things that they have been able to take for granted, so then the more strongly and widely it would be resisted" (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 138). There is this pervasive *conceptual inertia* in science: some insights become frozen into our evolving edifice of knowledge as we generate other insights that rely on them. And the more we build on them, the more constrained they become. Wimsatt calls this process *generative entrenchment*.

Generative entrenchment complements robustness. It focuses on downstream consequences rather than the intrinsic trustworthiness of an insight. The two usually go hand in hand: most entrenched insights are also robust because they are more likely to persist if they are stable from the outset. This results in *differential entrenchment*: some insights become entrenched while others do not. However, every once in a while, an entrenched insight turns out to be fragile. As Wimsatt puts it: "[a]n entrenched assumption is not necessarily true, and might even be empirically false, though we are in big trouble if it is not at least approximately true in most circumstances where it can be applied. We *need* it to be true" (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 143, *my emphasis*). In other words: we are prone to fool ourselves to keep up appearances, as the failure of an entrenched but fragile element can lead to the collapse of whole sections of our perceived knowledge. This is either a *disaster* (in Wimsatt's words), or a *scientific revolution*.

One of the most famous examples of the latter is Max Planck's realization that blackbody radiation is quantized, not continuous, which led to the development of quantum mechanics in the early 20th century. This is illusory robustness (as discussed in [section 3](#)): most scientists at the time simply took the continuous nature of radiation for granted. In contrast to this radical yet productive change, the current standard model of cosmology with all its mysterious dark matter and energy — an exercise in curve-fitting with phenomenological parameters — seems to be leaning towards disaster: a fragile edifice with few alternatives. Similar things can be said about superstring theory, another large theoretical construct which lacks robustness, since it is not experimentally testable — not now or in the foreseeable future. These major branches of cosmology and physics may have to be scrapped altogether. I said it before but I can't say it often enough: fundamental physics is a bad example for the special sciences to follow.

Generative entrenchment itself evolves. As in the case of robustness, entrenched knowledge components can not only become *more* entrenched (which they are prone to do as time goes on) but also get *disentrenched*, due to the reticulate and distributed nature of Babylonian science. Downstream insights may become robust themselves, and so their own reliance on an entrenched insight becomes redundant. Newton's assumption of *action at a distance* is a good example. For centuries, classical mechanics relied on the decidedly non-robust assumption that gravity (and other forces) can influence objects — almost magically — from afar. When Einstein's general-relativistic notion of spacetime curvature became robust, providing a more

plausible and naturalistic grounding for the action of gravity, Newton's entrenched but fragile account could easily be discarded. Of course, by that time, the scientific revolution that is relativity theory had already occurred, which made this disentanglement relatively painless.

To explain how differential entrenchment arises, Wimsatt introduces the idea of a *generative system*, which "facilitates mechanisms by which some elements can come to play a generative or foundational role relative to others" (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 135). The alphabet may be the most important generative system humanity has ever invented. It allows us to build knowledge on itself in a way that is fundamentally different from any oral tradition. But generative systems are not restricted to human knowledge or culture. They occur across levels: genetic replication and heredity are biological examples that enable effective evolution by natural selection. The genetic code is so heavily entrenched that very few (and only minor) variations of it exist. In general, Wimsatt argues, generative systems are "an extremely efficient way of building complex adaptive structures, while at the same time locking in its generators. Since these are two sides of the same coin, their association is a deep factor of nature" (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 137). Wherever there is evolution there are generative systems and entrenchment. They provide *scaffolding* for further innovation, and thus characterize evolution as a constructive process.

In the case of scientific knowledge, this scaffold — as you will recall from the [last section](#) — consists of false models of the world. This should no longer come as the shocking surprise it appears to be, because we now understand that *robust* does not equal *correct*. And false models are *useful*. In contrast, perfect models are not. There is nothing to build upon them, as they deal with the phenomena in their domain summarily. But, then, they are also not real. We can never know if we have truly captured all the relevant aspects of a system. And you rarely see a discussion section of a research paper stating that "all questions have been answered, and no further investigation into this topic will be required." Building knowledge means generating new (and hopefully better) questions. This is how your paper gets cited: it piques the interest of other researchers and induces them to do further research. Imperfection is the point! Or as Samuel Beckett put it, much more memorably: "Ever tried. Ever failed. No matter. Try again. Fail again. Fail better " (Beckett, 1983, p. 7).

7. Causal thickets: the special sciences truly *are* special

"Here if anywhere, philosophers may be useful if they know the lay of the land."
(Wimsatt, 2007, p. 238)

If you felt uncomfortable with levels breaking down into perspectives, I have bad news for you. The *curse of complexity* is to blame: the more complex a system gets, the more degrees of freedom it exhibits. This not only means that it has an increasingly large and flexible repertoire

of behaviors, but also that it can interact with all kinds of other systems, across levels, in all kinds of ways. At some point, the situation becomes so entangled that our perspectives can no longer solve any of the problems such a system poses. “Perspectives have now degenerated into a *causal thicket*” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 238, *my emphasis*).

This is the third major causal domain of our world — levels, perspectives, and thickets (Fig. 3). Causal thickets apply to parts of biology (multicellular organisms and ecology, in particular), most of neuroscience, plus all of psychology and the social sciences. In these domains, levels still exist, but intersect in such complex ways that boundaries between perspectives become blurred and eventually break down altogether. Disorder and ambiguity reign supreme — in a thicket, we’d better expect the unexpected! But perspectives do not simply go away. Instead, they multiply limitlessly. Wimsatt uses a vivid visual metaphor to illustrate this: “[p]erspectives may still seem to have an organizing power (just as viewing a thicket or shrub from different sides will reveal a shape to its bushy confusion), but there will be too many boundary disputes” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 238/9). We cannot seem to agree which view of the shrub represents its true nature and, unfortunately, there seem to be an infinite number of equally valid views.

Fig 3: Three causal domains: levels, perspectives, and thickets. Only the domains of the very large (cosmological) and the very small (atoms and molecules) cleanly separate into levels of organization. In between, levels overlap and increasingly break up into cross-level perspectives (at the cellular level and

above). In the multicellular, psychological, ecological, and social domains, even perspectives break down, leading to a causal thicket with an in(de)finite number of possible perspectives. See text for details. Inspired by Wimsatt (2007), Fig. 10.2 (pp. 232/3). Artwork by Marcus Neustetter.

"All of this enormously complicates talk of reduction, because with such multiply connected entities, and the failure of the ability to say what is composed of what, it may now be almost impossible to determine what is being reduced, what is doing the reducing, and what even is the proper scope of the system under analysis and the problem we are being asked to solve." (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 239). This would explain why modeling social dynamics using rational-choice models is such a terrible idea. There is simply too much going on — across intricately entangled levels — for simple reductionist heuristics to work. And the situation is highly volatile too: new kinds of organization emerge all of the time and constrain the underlying dynamics by downward causation in ways that are not only radically unpredictable, but cannot even be formally predated before they actually occur (Kauffman, 2000). Evidently, under these circumstances, robust insights and predictive models are really hard to come by.

As an example, let's look at attempts to model and predict the stock market. In this case, the bar for success seems fairly low: we know from experiences with insider trading that even the slightest predictive edge can result in massive gains if applied at scale. And, yet, attempts at providing such an edge by modeling have failed, again and again. The reasons for this should be obvious by now. They are rooted in the inherently *not* rational, and hence unpredictable, behavior of limited agents with incomplete information. Specifically: as soon as anyone actually predicts the market and changes their behavior accordingly, everybody else will rapidly follow suit by adjusting their own investment strategies. This means the predictive model no longer applies since it cannot reliably anticipate the behavioral change it itself will induce. The problem is that the model is an intrinsic part of the system: its mere existence imposes new organizational constraints, which invalidate it in the process. This is a prime example of feedback involving downward causation between levels, and illustrates why it is so hard — and perhaps entirely unworkable — to predictively model a causal thicket.

This kind of problem is serious, and applies widely across scientific disciplines that operate within causal thickets. It leads to *crises of reproducibility* and creates *pseudo-controversies* over interpretations of concepts and models that lack any robust grounding in reality.

Consider, for instance, how almost all terms used in the life and social sciences are overloaded with multiple meanings. Most of these concepts are therefore fragmentary, just like the concept of *levels* itself (Brooks, 2017, 2021a). *Information* is an excellent example. The problem is that its technical formulation (as Shannon entropy) excludes any consideration of semantic content, and only really applies to a very narrow domain of phenomena and problems

concerned with the transmission of (potentially meaningless) patterns. As soon as meaning enters the picture — and it always does when dealing with living beings — it becomes unclear how to define what information is, or how to operationalize it in order to measure its content. This, somewhat ironically, leads to so much miscommunication and misinterpretation — *misinformation*, frankly — that it is sometimes questionable whether the term still does any useful work for us at all. And, surely, we cannot derive any general conclusions from such an ill-defined concept. This illustrates why extending our local models is so incredibly challenging inside a thicket.

Thickets, and the lack of robustness they entail, have important practical consequences for scientific practice in all the affected sciences. To be honest: we often still do empirical and theoretical research wrong in these domains. Instead of reveling in pseudo-controversies, instead of turning a blind eye to the failures of our reductionist heuristics, instead of hoping for unified theories and a formal rigor that will never surface, we need to understand the true nature of the reality we are dealing with, and embrace the wide diversity of approaches that are needed to face the radical uncertainty that comes with such a situation. Wimsatt, as usual, does not beat about the bush: “an unusually large faction of the disputes should be resolvable as people from different groups learn and work out how to talk with one another, if (and it is a big sociological if) they maintain a commitment to try to understand one another rather than bloating their reputations by taking cheap shots at the opposition. This is perhaps the deepest pragmatic commitment of science — that it is in one’s interest to come to understand differences, and then to resolve them.” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 239/40).

This does *not* mean, however, that we should embrace what philosopher Richard Bernstein (1989) has called *flabby pluralism*. Even in a causal thicket, it is not true that every perspective is as good (or as bad) as any other. In any given context, there are models that will serve our purposes better than others. It all depends on what we expect from them. Bernstein calls this approach *engaged pluralism*: multiple perspectives are only desirable insofar as each makes a unique and useful contribution to our understanding of the problem at hand. Again, Wimsatt puts it best: “[science] yields an ultimately realist picture only because the world has an indefinitely large number of constraints for acceptable theories. If you know where to look. But you’d better get an overall sense of the geography before you decide on your colonizing strategy” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 240). And this is exactly — as the quote says at the beginning of [this section](#) — where philosophers may be most useful to you as a practitioner in the field.

Conclusion: making sense of the world as a rainforest

“One of the remarkable things about our universe is the degree of order we find in it.”
(Wimsatt, 2007, p.240)

After all is said and done, it is still striking how orderly our world really is. Wimsatt helps us understand why it couldn't be otherwise. Even though causal thickets are not a "wastebasket category," they are not the norm either — not some form of "ontological primordial slime" (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 240). Chaos does *not* rule (Fig. 1). If it did, it would hardly be possible for limited beings like us to arise, survive, and adapt to our environment through evolution.

Even if the world is not quite as predictable or comprehensible as we'd sometimes wish — even if it does resemble an entangled and ever-growing tropical rainforest more than Quine's lonely but uncomplicated desert ([section 2](#)) — we can still find our way around and make our home in the jungle. In fact, it's a much nicer place than that desert ... and by some margin. We need the jumble and the richness as much as the multilayered order. In other words, there is a deep and underexplored connection between our human capacity to lead meaningful lives, and the fact that we are limited epistemic agents inhabiting an ontological rainforest.

All of this is reflected in the creative and empirical successes of science, which are hard to deny. It not only yields robust, penetrating knowledge, but also produces a vast range of practical applications and technologies. Science works! If done right, it can make our lives more livable, keep us healthy and comfortable, help us orient ourselves and recognize our place. Wimsatt provides a realistic and workable explanation for why that is.

After all, even as limited and imperfect as humans are, we *can* get a good enough grip on reality, although in a way that is much more down-to-earth — and much more improvised — than most philosophers or physicists working on fundamental theories would care to let on. The multilayered order of the world is far from regular or exceptionless. It is not "crystalline without flaw" (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 240). And we are error-prone beings; the knowledge we produce is always situated and fallible. But we can still discern regularities at all levels and formulate perspectives that tie them together — at least locally. "This looks a lot more complex than the old story, but it provides tools and ways of thinking and talking which seem a lot closer to the truth. And, as I've been trying to tell you, that's the way the world is" (*ibid.*).

This isn't just theoretical speculation. It is supported by plenty of observations that provide empirical evidence for how science actually works in practice. I have illustrated, using concrete examples, how heuristics are applied and exapted, when they fail, and how we can learn from those failures. This is what Wimsatt means by a *theory of practice*: it is a *taxonomy of heuristics* — not abstract Greek-style metaphysics, but a Babylonian web of connected models that may be idealized, but are robustly grounded in reality. In spirit, this is closely related to what we now call the *science of science* (Fortunato et al., 2018). Sadly, Wimsatt is rarely read or cited by practitioners in that field, even though his philosophy is evidently very relevant to their work.

In contrast, the foundationalist theories of knowledge that we like to keep around — for our own comfort and confidence, it seems, more than anything else — are not only impractical, but flat out misleading if we truly want to understand ourselves, the world, and our place in it. In their every-day practice, Wimsatt points out, scientists adjust their idealizations to reality, but when representing science towards the public, we often fit reality to our idealizations. It is high time that not only philosophers but also practicing scientists acknowledge this and move on.

As an example, consider the view that all *physics is computation* (introduced in [section 1](#)). A perspectival realist would not come up with such an idea, but would recognize it for what it is: mistaking the map for the territory — what philosopher and mathematician Alfred North Whitehead (1925) called the *fallacy of misplaced concreteness*. It confuses our abstract descriptions of reality (how we compute) with actual reality (how effects get caused in the world). It is a god-like *view from nowhere* which assumes that what's in our mind is all there is.

Such a view has no place in a naturalistic philosophy for limited beings. And, precisely because it assumes limitless power and insight, it quickly leads to absurd conclusions. One of these confuses the simulation of agential and conscious behavior in “artificial intelligence” for actual agency and consciousness in living beings (Roli et al., 2022; Jaeger, 2024a; Jaeger et al., 2024). Another is the idea that we *live* in a computer simulation. This may be the ultimate map-and-territory fallacy. Finally, there is the suggestion that we can literally reprogram reality — that it is possible and desirable to control and engineer every natural system we encounter. This is dangerous hubris, and is bound to lead to the kind of unintended consequences that *are* likely to kill us eventually.

What we must realize — for a more realistic and sustainable view — is that it is not just us, but also our scientific knowledge and our scientific instruments that constantly co-evolve. It should be quite obvious: science is not a static or steadily expanding repository of objective facts, but an irregular process that keeps on adapting our insights and actions to our current situation. It is a powerful recipe to debug our error-prone heuristics. And it does this admirably well — more efficiently than any other form of knowledge production that humans have developed so far.

Yet, science remains imperfect. And, Wimsatt tells us, this is not a flaw, but one of its most essential features. It is *false* models that lead to truer insights. Those are the kind of models we can learn from and build on. The aim of science has never been certainty, or completeness — not globally contradiction-free theories — but the most robust path towards local adaptation given the limited tools and resources we actually have available. And this process never ends. The mere idea of a “theory of everything” should appear incoherent to you by now. It is not

only unattainable, but there is no reason why we would want a theory like that in the first place. A map with everything on it is *not* useful; it is just an exact copy of the territory. And we do not want to (and probably can't) live in a territory like the one this map would depict. A chaotic world, without any order, may be adverse to life, but so is a closed and deterministic clockwork, based on a limited and well-defined set of rules and components (*cf.* [section 2](#); Fig. 1).

But, not to worry: everything we've learnt so far points to the robust fact that our world is *not* conceptually closed or predetermined in this way — that our future is, in fact, radically open. Our peculiar and limited perspective on reality emerges from our interactions with a reality that is, ultimately, far beyond our grasp or control. We cannot even appreciate what it would mean to have complete knowledge (*cf.* [section 1](#)). How would we ever recognize that we truly understand everything there is to know? It makes no sense. Intelligent beings always find new ways of exploring their large world. Isn't that a comforting thought? We grow (wiser, hopefully) and discover more fascinating things. Isn't this what life is all about for any limited being?

Looking at scientific knowledge itself as a *complex adaptive system* shifts our focus away from traditional philosophical issues — such as the realism/instrumentalism debate I mentioned in [section 3](#), or the problem of how to demarcate science from pseudo-science by some simple and general criterion — towards aspects it shares with other complex evolutionary processes. Science distinguishes itself from other ways of knowing by degree, in how it *does* things that lead to trustworthy, useful, and (ideally) generalizable insights. And it does things in all kinds of ways, depending on what works in different situations: there is no rigidly unified method. This is another one of its strengths — diversity, after all, is a prerequisite for adaptation.

All of this explains why Wimsatt likes to compare the evolution of knowledge via *conceptual engineering* — think of it as the evolution of populations of insights — with the Darwinian evolution of populations of organisms. It allows him to identify a number of basic and general features that both processes have in common if we consider them in the abstract:

1. *Robustness* — implies multiple, independent connections to other components of the process. A robust insight is accessible in many different ways, while a robust organism develops in a failsafe manner and has many versatile interactions with its environment. In general, robustness provides the stability required for selective pressures to do their work.
2. *Heuristics* — are efficient but context-sensitive and fallible tools for problem solving. They are themselves the product of selective processes, and correspond to adaptive behaviors in biological evolution. Living is improvising: heuristics may not yield optimal solutions, but they allow imperfect creatures and ideas to satisfice in their given situation.

3. *Generative entrenchment* — describes the inertia of insights or biological factors on which many other insights and factors depend. Differential entrenchment means that robust features of an evolutionary process are more likely to become entrenched. Entrenchment provides the constructive scaffold on which innovation can build.
4. *Near-decomposability* — characterizes the (imperfect) modularity that limits entrenchment and prevents the evolutionary process from becoming frozen in time. It does this by keeping the consequences of changes and failures localized. This is crucial for piecewise engineering of knowledge and the evolvability of biological traits and organisms.

The idea is not to claim that biological evolution and the evolution of scientific knowledge are *literally* the same. Their underlying mechanisms differ considerably — not least, knowledge evolution being rather Lamarckian. The idea is also not to give competition between insights and theories center stage — some kind of naïve “survival of the fittest” or “marketplace of ideas” account of science. Quite the contrary: basic research often benefits from collaboration (especially across disciplinary boundaries). There are more perspectives to explore than researchers who can possibly explore them.

Instead, the point of highlighting broad commonalities between these evolutionary processes is to arrive at an eminently simple, basic, and practical insight: We are extremely unlikely to ever obtain an ultimate foundation for our knowledge — not through science, nor through any other way of knowing — but we can, so far as possible, give a robust account of how our knowledge *improves* and *adapts* under real-world circumstances. This is how *we get a tight enough grip on reality*, which is as good as it gets. This may not exactly be what we had originally hoped for. But, at least, “[w]e have become more aware, practically speaking, of what we really can and cannot do” (Wimsatt, 2007, p. 320). And what could be more important for a practicing scientist to know? Or for any limited being, for that matter? Herein lies the beauty of Wimsatt’s realism: it is humble, yet also solid ... and utterly achievable — it is a truly *human* kind of realism.

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References

- Atkins, P. W., Paula, J. D., & Keeler, J. (2022). *Physical Chemistry* (12th ed.). Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.
- Beckett, S. (1983). *Worstward Ho*. Grove Press, New York, NY, U.S.A.
- Bernstein, R. J. (1989). Pragmatism, Pluralism and the Healing of Wounds. *Proc Addr Am Phil Assoc*, 63(3), 5–18.
- Bhaskar, R. (1975). *A Realist Theory of Science*. Routledge, New York, NY, U.S.A.
- Bird, A. (2025). Thomas Kuhn. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2025). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, U.S.A. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2025/entries/thomas-kuhn>
- Bradie, M., & Harms, W. (2023). Evolutionary Epistemology. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2023). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, U.S.A. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2023/entries/epistemology-evolutionary>
- Brooks, D. S. (2017). In Defense of Levels: Layer Cakes and Guilt by Association. *Biol Theor*, 12(3), 142–56. DOI: [10.1007/s13752-017-0272-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13752-017-0272-8)
- Brooks, D. S. (2021a). A New Look at ‘Levels of Organization’ in Biology. *Erkenntnis*, 86(6), 1483–508. DOI: [10.1007/s10670-019-00166-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10670-019-00166-7)
- Brooks, D. S. (2021b). Levels of Organization as Tool and Doctrine in Biology. In D. S. Brooks, J. DiFrisco, & W. C. Wimsatt (Eds.), *Levels of Organization in the Biological Sciences* (pp. 39–60). The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, U.S.A. DOI: [10.7551/mitpress/12389.003.0006](https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12389.003.0006)
- Brooks, D. S., & Eronen, M. I. (2018). The significance of levels of organization for scientific research: A heuristic approach. *Stud Hist Phil Sci C: Biol Biomed Sci*, 68–69, 34–41. DOI: [10.1016/j.shpsc.2018.04.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.shpsc.2018.04.003)
- Brush, S. G. (1974). Should the History of Science Be Rated X? *Science*, 183(4130), 1164–1172.
- Campbell, D. T. (1974). Evolutionary Epistemology. In P. A. Schilpp (Ed.), *The Philosophy of Karl Popper* (Vol. 2, pp. 412–463). Open Court, LaSalle, IL, U.S.A.
- Cartwright, N. (1983). *How the Laws of Physics Lie*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.
- Cartwright, N. (1999). *The Dappled World: A Study of the Boundaries of Science*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- Chang, H. (2022). *Realism for Realistic People: A New Pragmatist Philosophy of Science*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- Creath, R. (2023). Logical Empiricism. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2023). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, U.S.A. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2023/entries/logical-empiricism>

- Culp, S. (1994). Defending Robustness: The Bacterial Mesosome as a Test Case. *PSA 1994* (Vol. 1, pp. 257–272). D. Reidel Publishing Company, Dordrecht, NL.
DOI: [10.1086/psaprocbienmeetp.1994.1.193010](https://doi.org/10.1086/psaprocbienmeetp.1994.1.193010)
- Culp, S. (1995). Objectivity in Experimental Inquiry: Breaking Data-Technique Circles. *Phil Sci* 62(3): 438–58. DOI: [10.1086/289877](https://doi.org/10.1086/289877)
- Deacon, T. W. (2011). *Incomplete Nature: How Mind Emerged from Matter*. W. W. Norton & Company, New York, NY, U.S.A.
- Dupré, J. (1993). *The Disorder of Things: Metaphysical Foundations of the Disunity of Science*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA, U.S.A.
- Eronen, M. I., & Brooks, D. S. (2024). Levels of Organization in Biology. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Summer 2024). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, U.S.A.
<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/sum2024/entries/levels-org-biology>
- Feyerabend, P. (1975). *Against Method*. New Left Books, London, UK.
- Feynman, R. P. (1965). *The Character of Physical Law*. BBC, London, UK.
Video lectures available online: <https://youtu.be/kEx-qRfuhhk>
- Fortunato, S., Bergstrom, C. T., Börner, K., Evans, J. A., Helbing, D., Milojević, S., Petersen, A. M., Radicchi, F., Sinatra, R., Uzzi, B., Vespignani, A., Waltman, L., Wang, D., & Barabási, A.-L. (2018). Science of science. *Science*, 359(6379), eaao0185. DOI: [10.1126/science.aao0185](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao0185)
- Frank, A., Gleiser, M., & Thompson, E. (2024). *The Blind Spot: Why Science Cannot Ignore Human Experience*. The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, U.S.A.
- Gettier, E. L. (1963). Is justified true belief knowledge? *Analysis*, 23(6), 121–3.
DOI: [10.1093/analys/23.6.121](https://doi.org/10.1093/analys/23.6.121)
- Giere, R. N. (1999). *Science without Laws*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL, U.S.A.
- Giere, R. N. (2006). *Scientific Perspectivism*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL, U.S.A.
- Gould, S. J., & Vrba, E. S. (1982). Exaptation—A Missing Term in the Science of Form. *Paleobiology*, 8(1), 4–15. DOI: [10.1017/S0094837300004310](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0094837300004310)
- Hacking, I. (1983). *Representing and Intervening: Introductory Topics in the Philosophy of Natural Science*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- Hartl, D. L., & Clark, A. G. (2007). *Principles of Population Genetics* (4th ed.). Sinauer Associates, Sunderland, MA, U.S.A.
- Hofmeyr, J.-H. S. (2021). A biochemically-realizable relational model of the self-manufacturing cell. *Biosystems*, 207, 104463. DOI: [10.1016/j.biosystems.2021.104463](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystems.2021.104463)
- Hofstadter, D. R. (2007). *I Am a Strange Loop*. Basic Books, New York, NY, U.S.A.
- Jaeger, J. (2024a). Artificial intelligence is algorithmic mimicry: Why artificial “agents” are not (and won’t be) proper agents. *NBDT*, 1–21. DOI: [10.51628/001c.94404](https://doi.org/10.51628/001c.94404)

- Jaeger, J. (2024b). The Fourth Perspective: Evolution and Organismal Agency. In M. Mossio (Ed.), *Organization in Biology* (pp. 159–186). Springer Intl. Publishing, Cham, CH.
DOI: [10.1007/978-3-031-38968-9_8](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-38968-9_8)
- Jaeger, J., Riedl, A., Djedovic, A., Vervaeke, J., & Walsh, D. (2024). Naturalizing relevance realization: Why agency and cognition are fundamentally not computational. *Front Psych*, *15*, 1362658.
DOI: [10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1362658](https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1362658)
- Kauffman, S. A. (1971). Articulation of Parts Explanation in Biology and the Rational Search for Them. In R. C. Buck & R. S. Cohen (Eds.), *PSA 1970* (Vol. 8, pp. 257–272). D. Reidel Publishing Company, Dordrecht, NL. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-010-3142-4_18
- Kauffman, S. A. (2000). *Investigations*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.
- Kingsland, S. E. (1995). *Modeling Nature: Episodes in the History of Population Ecology* (2nd ed.). University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL, U.S.A.
- Knuuttila, T., & Loettgers, A. (2014). Magnets, Spins, and Neurons: The Dissemination of Model Templates Across Disciplines. *The Monist*, *97*(3), 280–300.
DOI: [10.5840/monist201497319](https://doi.org/10.5840/monist201497319)
- Knuuttila, T., & Loettgers, A. (2016). Model templates within and between disciplines: From magnets to gases – and socio-economic systems. *Eur J Phil Sci*, *6*(3), 377–400.
DOI: [10.1007/s13194-016-0145-1](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13194-016-0145-1)
- Knuuttila, T., & Loettgers, A. (2023). Model templates: Transdisciplinary application and entanglement. *Synthese*, *201*(6), 200. DOI: [10.1007/s11229-023-04178-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11229-023-04178-3)
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago, IL, U.S.A.
- Ladyman, J. (2002). *Understanding Philosophy of Science*. Routledge, New York, NY, U.S.A.
- Ladyman, J., Lambert, J., & Wiesner, K. (2013). What is a complex system? *Eur J Phil Sci*, *3*(1), 33–67. DOI: [10.1007/s13194-012-0056-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/s13194-012-0056-8)
- Lakatos, I. (1970). Falsification and the Methodology of Scientific Research Programmes. In I. Lakatos & A. Musgrave (Eds.), *Criticism and the Growth of Knowledge* (pp. 91–196). Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.
- Levins, R. (1966). The Strategy of Model Building in Population Biology. *Am Sci*, *54*(4), 421–31.
- Ludwig, D., & Ruphy, S. (2024). Scientific Pluralism. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Fall 2024). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, U.S.A.
<https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/fall2024/entries/scientific-pluralism>
- Massimi, M. (2016). Four Kinds of Perspectival Truth. *Phil Phenom Res*, *96*(2), 342–359.
DOI: [10.1111/phpr.12300](https://doi.org/10.1111/phpr.12300)
- Massimi, M. (2022). *Perspectival Realism*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.

- Massimi, M., & McCoy, C. D. (2020). *Understanding Perspectivism: Scientific Challenges and Methodological Prospects*. Routledge, New York, NY, U.S.A.
- Maturana, H. R., & Varela, F. J. (1987). *The Tree of Knowledge: The Biological Roots of Human Understanding*. Shambhala, Boston, MA, U.S.A.
- Montévil, M., & Mossio, M. (2015). Biological organisation as closure of constraints. *J Theor Biol*, 372, 179–91. DOI: [10.1016/j.jtbi.2015.02.029](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtbi.2015.02.029)
- Moreno, A., & Mossio, M. (2015). *Biological Autonomy*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, NL.
- Musgrave, A., & Pigden, C. (2023). Imre Lakatos. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2023). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, U.S.A. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2023/entries/lakatos>
- Oberheim, E., & Preston, J. (2025). Paul Feyerabend. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Spring 2025). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, U.S.A. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/spr2025/entries/feyerabend>
- Pattee, H. H., & Rączaszek-Leonardi, J. (2012). *Laws, language and life: Howard Pattee's classic papers on the physics of symbols with contemporary commentary*. Springer Netherlands, Dordrecht, NL. DOI: [10.1007/978-94-007-5161-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-5161-3)
- Quine, W. V. O. (1948). On What There Is. *Rev Metaphys*, 2(1), 21–38.
- Quine, W. V. O. (1951). Two Dogmas of Empiricism. *Phil Rev*, 60(1), 20–43. DOI: [10.2307/2266637](https://doi.org/10.2307/2266637)
- Roli, A., Jaeger, J., & Kauffman, S.A. (2022). How Organisms Come to Know the World: Fundamental Limits on Artificial General Intelligence. *Front Ecol Evol* 9: 806283. DOI: [10.3389/fevo.2021.806283](https://doi.org/10.3389/fevo.2021.806283)
- Rosen, R. (1985). *Anticipatory Systems: Philosophical, Mathematical, and Methodological Foundations* (1st edition). Pergamon Press, Oxford, UK.
- Rosen, R. (1991). *Life Itself: A Comprehensive Inquiry into the Nature, Origin, and Fabrication of Life*. Columbia University Press, New York, NY, U.S.A.
- Savage, L. J. (1954). *The Foundations of Statistics*. John Wiley & Sons, New York, NY, U.S.A.
- Simon, H. A. (1955). A Behavioral Model of Rational Choice. *Quart J Econ*, 69(1), 99–118. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1884852>
- Simon, H. A. (1962). The Architecture of Complexity. *Proc Am Phil Soc*, 106(6), 467–82.
- Simon, H. A. (1969). *The Sciences of the Artificial*. The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, U.S.A.
- Thornton, S. (2023). Karl Popper. In E. N. Zalta & U. Nodelman (Eds.), *The Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (Winter 2023). Metaphysics Research Lab, Stanford University, Stanford, CA, U.S.A. <https://plato.stanford.edu/archives/win2023/entries/popper>
- Varela, F. J. (1979). *Principles of Biological Autonomy*. North Holland, New York, NY, U.S.A.

- Waddington, C. H. (1957). *The Strategy of the Genes: A Discussion of Some Aspects of Theoretical Biology*. Allen & Unwin, London, UK.
- Watson, A. J., & Lovelock, J. E. (1983). Biological homeostasis of the global environment: The parable of Daisyworld. *Tellus B: Chem Phys Meteorol*, 35(4), 284–289.
DOI: [10.3402/tellusb.v35i4.14616](https://doi.org/10.3402/tellusb.v35i4.14616)
- Whitehead, A. N. (1925). *Science and the Modern World*. Macmillan, London, UK.
- Wimsatt, W. C. (2007). *Re-Engineering Philosophy for Limited Beings: Piecewise Approximations to Reality*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, MA, U.S.A.
- Wimsatt, W. C. (2021). Levels, Robustness, Emergence, and Heterogeneous Dynamics: Finding Partial Organization in Causal Thickets. In D. S. Brooks, J. DiFrisco, & W. C. Wimsatt (Eds.), *Levels of Organization in the Biological Sciences* (pp. 21–38). The MIT Press, Cambridge, MA, U.S.A. DOI: [10.7551/mitpress/12389.003.0005](https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/12389.003.0005)